

Major insect pests of wetland rice in Guyana, South America.

Growth stage	Pest		Damage
	Scientific name	Common name	
Emergence to maximum tillering	1. <i>Helodytes foveolatus</i> Duval (Curculionidae: Coleoptera)	Rice water weevil	Larva feeds on roots. Adult feeds on eye of pre-germinated seeds.
	2. <i>Hydrellia deonieri</i> Rambajan (Ephydriidae: Diptera)	Rice leafminer Rice blackfly	Larva feeds in growing shoot, causes deadheart.
	3. <i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i> (Smith) (Noctuidae: Lepidoptera)	Fall armyworm	Larva feeds on seedling leaves, causes burnt tip, later defoliation.
	4. <i>Mocis punctularis</i> Hubner (Noctuidae: Lepidoptera)	Rice looper	
	5. <i>Neoconocephalus</i> Spp. <i>Caulopsis</i> Spp. (Tettigoniidae: Orthoptera)	Long-horned grass-hopper	Feeds on leaves that appear shredded, cobweb.
Panicle initiation to heading	1. <i>Caulopsis cupsidata</i> Scudder (Tettigoniidae: Orthoptera)	Long-horned grass-hopper	Feeds on leaves and ball, causes whitehead.
Heading to hard dough	1. <i>Oebalus poecilus</i> Dallas (Pentatomidae: Hemiptera)	Stink bug or paddy bug	Nymph and adult feed on grains at milk stage, cause wind paddy or atrophied glumes; at dough stage cause broken barrels, discolored rice after milling.
Hard dough to harvest, storage	1. <i>Sitotroga cerealella</i> (Olivier) (Gelechiidae: Lepidoptera)	Angoumois grain moth	Larva feeds on kernel.
	2. <i>Rhyzopertha dominica</i> (Fabricius) (Bostrichidae: Coleoptera)	Lesser grain borer	

Rice gall midge incidence in the dry season

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Rice gall midge (*Orseolia oryzae*), a major insect pest in late-planted fields in the wet season (May-November) in the Andhra Pradesh Krishna and Godavari deltas, has become a major problem in the dry season (November-April) in the Godavari delta since 1978. The percentage silver shoots or galls recorded in

Percent silver shoots in dry season, Maruteru, India.

Trial	Silver shoots (%)			
	1979		1980	
	Mean	Maximum	Mean	Maximum
Uniform Variety Trial 2	11	20	5	8
Uniform Variety Trial 3	17	24	18	25
Uniform Variety Trial 4	16	28	13	8

coordinated variety trials show the high pressure of gall midge at Maruteru center (see table).

It is likely that extensive use of pesticides to control insects has resulted in the destruction of predators and parasites of

rice gall midge. Popular *rabi season* varieties Jaya, Prabhat, Prakash, Rasi, and Tella Hamsa are susceptible to rice gall midge. BPT1235 and IR36 are promising early-maturing, gall midge-resistant varieties. ■

Effects of rice plant age on diopsis oviposition and plant susceptibility

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Diopsis thoracica (West), a serious pest limiting rice yields in West Africa, prefers plants of particular ages for oviposition. Confirmation of the specific age range would be useful in planning pest management programs involving host plant resistance and other control measures.

Pregerminated seeds of 2 rice varieties

Diopsis thoracica eggs laid on rice plants of different ages and subsequent development of dead-hearts in Sierra Leone.^a

DT ^b	IR5			GH106-76		
	Eggs (no.)	Dead-hearts (no.)	Dead-hearts/egg (no.)	Eggs (no.)	Dead-hearts (no.)	Dead-hearts/egg (no.)
10	4 cd	6 b	1.5	2 ab	4 ab	2.0
20	11 ab	13 a	1.2	2 ab	3 b	1.5
30	14 a	14 a	1.0	5 a	6 a	1.2
40	8 bc	6 b	0.8	3 ab	3 b	1.0
50	2 d	2 c	1.0	1 b	0	0.0
60	1 d	0 c	0.0	0 b	0	0.0

^aTotal of 6 replications. In the same column, means followed by the same letter do not differ at the 1% level of probability. ^bDT = days after transplanting.

with similar tillering abilities, IR5 and GH106-76, were sown at 10-day intervals. Seedlings 21 days after sowing

(DS) were transplanted separately at 2 seedlings/pot. Rice plants 60, 50, 40, 30, 20, and 10 days after transplanting (DT)